

EVIDENCE-BASED FLIPPED CLASSROOM CASE STUDY – TEACHING CHEMICAL PROCESS SAFETY

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Abstract

This paper provides a case study of how Evidence-Based Teaching (EBT) was applied to a flipped classroom format and implemented in a core module *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* from the Diploma in Chemical Engineering from Singapore Polytechnic. The paper firstly outlines the plant lifecycle approach which served as an advanced organizer for students' learning of the main outcomes in this module. This is followed by a summary of the curriculum restructuring and introduction of the pedagogic framework adopted. In particular, it shows how the out-of-class (online) components are pedagogically aligned to in-class activities and technology tools are integrated to strategically and creatively enhance key aspects of the learning process. The paper then, based on work done during the first 6 weeks of the programme, illustrates how the framework is effectively applied in real online and classroom contexts. This includes a comprehensive week-by-week teaching plan which guides the design of suitable learning activities, both in-class and out-of-class, using core principles of learning. These learning activities are designed to scaffold students learning the underlying key concepts that lead to application in real-world problem-solving. Evidence of student learning is captured using Web 2.0 Tools such as Socrative, Google Doc, etc. These are communicated as formative feedback to students, often in real-time when possible. Connections between key concepts and transfer of learning from case studies learnt in class to solving real-world problems (albeit some simulated) are emphasized throughout the learning process. Sample marking rubrics to assist students in understanding learning expectations are prepared and communicated to students. Mock tests are conducted whereby students are given opportunities to use the rubrics to mark their own paper as well as carrying out peer marking. Examples of evidence gathered, their analysis and feedback given to students are shared, providing important two way feedback relating to both task specific and process aspects of the learning activities. Finally, the paper presents the result of an interim evaluation of the students learning experience to date and key instructional issues identified.

Keywords: Evidence-based teaching, flipped classroom, formative assessment, chemical engineering

Introduction

The pedagogy for evidence-based flipped classroom has been shared previously by Cheah (2016). The module in this case study is entitled *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention*, a Year 3 Diploma in Chemical Engineering core module (60 hours, fully in-course, i.e. no examinations) taught to all 120 students in Semester 1 of an academic year. The framework used in teaching the module is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Framework for Teaching Chemical Process Safety based on Plant Lifecycle (Cheah, 2015)

The module is taught over a period of 15 weeks using case study as the core pedagogic method. Contact hours are 4 hours per week which is devoted to classroom activities designed to engage students in applying the concepts learned during the online components. The main learning outcomes from the module are:

1. Identify from the assigned cases the correct safety issues at the proper stage of the chemical plant lifecycle
2. Infer and interpret probable causes that can lead to deviation from safe operating conditions and predict likely consequences or damages
3. Apply the correct preventive or mitigation strategies to prevent the occurrence or minimize the impact of any occurrence of a chemical process hazard
4. Transfer key concepts and principles from analysis of earlier cases to new cases presented at a later part of the semester

These outcomes frame the type of assessment evidence to be derived from the various student activities.

Summary of Work Done

The flipped classroom approach was used to teach this module for the first time in Semester 1 of Academic Year 2015, which began in April and ended in August. The approach and methods adopted have been presented elsewhere by Cheah et al (2016). A major learning point from the pilot work was the need for a higher level of facilitation skills by lecturers to facilitate these challenging learning outcomes.

Figure 2. Example of an Evidence-based Flipped Classroom Format (Cheah, 2016)

The work presented here is the re-designed model using an Evidence-Based Teaching (EBT) approach (e.g. Petty, 2009; Hattie, 2009), employing various high effect size strategies such as challenging goals, feedback, and advance organizer. The framework in Figure 1 was in fact, used as an advance organizer to help students learn this module. A workbook is also provided to help students work through the classroom activities. For each week, a set of guidance notes are given to students, which explain in greater detail the

topics and learning outcomes for the week, as well as the resources made available. These notes are given to students ahead of their weekly lessons so that they can better prepare for the flipped classroom. Figure 2, illustrates the revised curriculum plan of the module for Semester 1, Academic Year 2016, based on an EBT flipped format (Cheah, 2016). The teaching plan for the first 6 weeks is shown in Figure 3.

	Flipped	In-Class Activities using ATU	
Week 1		Principles of Loss Prevention, How to Learn this Module, Expectations	Flixborough, Plant lifecycle as Advanced Organizer, Bhopal as "Anchor" case
Week 2	Inherently Safer Design (ISD), Management of Change (MOC)	Bhopal ISD, MOC; Guided Discussion on ATU Process Description + P&IDs	Google Doc submission on Questions for ATU Process Description + P&IDs
Week 3	Self-learn steady state simulation exercises + Mock Assignment	Bhopal LOPA: BPCS + SIS W318 Distillation Pilot Plant (DPP) LOPA	Google Doc: Discussion on PD+P&IDs Peer Marking of Mock Assignment
Week 3 (cont'd)	Basic Process Control System (BPCS) & Safety Instrumented System (SIS)	ATU Concept Checkpoint on BPCS & SIS Apply BPCS & SIS to ATU HP Absorber	Mock Test: Apply BPCS & SIS to ATU LP Absorber (Guided Self-Assessment)
Week 4	Pressure Relief System (PRS) Video: BP Texas, Site visit to W318 DPP PRS	Bhopal relief scenarios + extras (BP Texas, etc) Apply PRS to DPP	Apply PRS to ATU HP Absorber, Self-learn ATU Malfunction exercises
Week 5	Hazard & Operability Study (HAZOP), Info on Olefin Dimerization	HAZOP for Bhopal + other exercises (BP Texas, etc)	HAZOP for Olefin Dimerization, Mock HAZOP for selected ATU unit
Week 6	Complete ATU Malfunction exercises, Reading on proposed ATU Modification	Google Doc discussion on ATU malfunctions, Peer Marking ATU HAZOP	Discussion: HAZOP for new plant vs plant modification: Case of ATU

Figure 3. Module Structure for Weeks 1 to 6

In this mode of learning, every week from week 2 onwards, students come to class after going through key safety concepts on their own in the online components. These are mostly video recordings of the lectures, created with the content development tool, Camtasia, and, where appropriate, supplemented by reading materials either from published literature, curated by the author, and suitable videos from YouTube or the U.S. Chemical Safety Board (CSB). At the end of each lesson, students can choose to complete a short quiz

(usually 4-5 multiple-choice and/or true/false questions, created using Web 2.0 tools such as Socrative) as self-assessment of their understanding of the key concepts and principles underpinning the structure of the topics covered. When in class, the lecturer will first show the advance organizer (Figure 1) to help students track the progress of the lessons. He/she will then give a brief summary covering the key points of the flipped lessons. A mini-lecture is given if results from Socrative showed a significant number of students did not fully grasp the concepts. The lesson then proceeds with the lecturer providing relevant activities to engage students in applying the concepts learned. These activities are based on the Bhopal Gas Disaster as an “anchor” case study, supplemented with other cases such as Piper Alpha and BP Texas Explosion. For facilitating transfer of knowledge to new cases, we designed a new case study based on the Amine Treating Unit (ATU) dynamic simulation model from EnVision. We also introduce new cases where appropriate to give students additional practice in applying what they are learning.

For example, as shown in Figure 4, the majority of students are quite clear that answers C and D are correct examples of Safety Instrumented System (SIS), but not so certain between answers A and B. As it turned out, the majority of students selected the wrong answer 'A', which means that they still had difficulty applying the concept of SIS (safety instrumented system) to certain aspects of chemical plant operation. The lecturer then uses necessary classroom time clarifying the concept further with other examples or analogies.

Figure 4. Sample result from Socrative

Classroom discussions utilize Google Doc, whereby a class of 18-22 students is divided into 4-5 groups of 4-5 students each. Students discuss within their groups and present a group answer to the questions posed by typing in real time into the response box created in Google Doc. In some situations, students are asked questions that have more than one correct answer, so each group is required to provide a different answer. In other situations, different questions are asked to each group, so that they need to collaboratively come up with parts of the answer in order to obtain a complete solution.

Area of Application of Loss Prevention Principles	Case of Bhopal (explain why it is not desirable)	How application of Inherently Safer Design can reduce the hazard(s).
Plant operation	Refrigeration system decommissioned for a long time. Safety interlocks bypassed. Vent scrubber decommissioned. SOP not followed, blind not inserted. Flare tower under maintenance since long time ago, not enough manpower. Control instruments such as T and P gauges not working properly	(Design) Moderate - The refrigeration system should never be decommissioned to ensure safer storage of MIC. YES! That is correct. Minimise - Storage of MIC should be done in smaller tanks. 10 small tanks are safer than 3 large tanks. Better still and to adhere strictly to the principles of ISD: have 3 smaller tanks. Otherwise the tendency is to fill all 10 small tanks! Substitute - Since water reacts with MIC in an exothermic reaction, alternative material such as nitrogen or plant air can be used to purge or wash the pipes during maintenance Good thinking. You got that right!
Plant layout and design	There was supposed to be four vent gas scrubbers for stand-by. Since in Bhopal there was only one vent gas scrubber. There was no standby vent for maintenance. The capacity of the flare is incapable in managing the volume of waste gas produced.	Vent, flares etc are not part of inherently safer design. They are 'add-ons' installed to mitigate any consequence of MIC leak. They fall under the active (as opposed to passive) protection strategies. Since this group identify the area of loss prevention as "Plant layout and design", for the layout part you could consider the location of the plant - it is close to slum areas where a large population existed. One can SUBSTITUTE this location with one which is safer, and not have the wind blowing MIC in its direction.
Plant design of construction	Using carbon steel instead of stainless steel for plant design. After a long time, rust will form which is the catalyst that triggers the reaction between MIC and water.	Substitute - Use stainless steel instead to reduce the chance of formation of rust hence reducing the amount of catalyst produced, thus leading to a slower reaction between MIC and water even when there is water flow into tanks. GOOD - you got this right!
OVERALL COMMENTS: Most of the answers above centred about Plant Design or Operations. Remember that more can be achieved by considering Process Development at the earliest opportunity, at the R&D stage. One can consider not using this reaction chemistry between phosgene (itself a toxic substance) and MMA altogether, and use something much less hazardous. This will achieve the aim of SUBSTITUTE of ISD. If really the MIC route must be used, then the next best thing to do is to MINIMISE the quantity of MIC stored on-site.		

Figure 5. Sample entries in Google Doc

A sample of Google Doc entry is shown in Figure 5, where most students are able to apply broad principles of loss prevention to different stages of plant lifecycle, but some are confused between safety strategies that are

inherently safer and those which are added on (such as vent and flare) to mitigate the risk. Student responses in this example also revealed that most, if not all of them, had overlooked an important aspect of loss prevention, which is to handle hazards at the process development stage, which is highlighted by the lecturer in his overall comments. This ongoing formative assessment, which fosters effective two-way feedback, is a high effect method in terms of student attainment (effect size of 0.73, Hattie (2009)).

There are 2 summative assessment after 6 weeks of lessons (Figure 3). One is the mid-semester test scheduled for week 7. Topics tested include inherently safer design (ISD) and Layer of Protection Analysis (LOPA). The other is a HAZOP Report due at end of Week 8. Coupled with the ongoing formative assessment (feedback) mentioned earlier, we created opportunities for students to receive adequate practice before taking the graded (summative) assessment. As noted in the literature, repeated testing results in promoting transfer of learning gained in one context to other new contexts (e.g. Rohrer, Taylor & Sholar, 2010; Carpenter, 2012).

Questions 1, 2 and 3	Level 4: Exceeding Expectation	Level 3: Meeting Expectation	Level 2: Approaching Expectation	Level 1: Poor or Below Expectation
Explanation of Observation Noted	Offer good explanations and deep analysis to all observations, including both that changed and those that did not change; plus additional insights inferred from the observations.	Noted which process variable changed and which do not, but offer only surface explanation to the observations, i.e. still lack deeper analysis or insights.	Only noted those process variable that changes, but failed to account satisfactorily for the changes, i.e. missed out on certain important analysis.	Little or no mention of any noteworthy observation, nor any effort in offering explanations for the changes observed.
Use of Evidence	Excellent use of data to support observation noted and referenced all pertinent tag numbers and corresponding PVs.	Satisfactory use of data to support observation noted and made good reference to some (but not all) tag numbers and their corresponding PVs.	Some use of correct data but linkage to observation noted is weak or lack clarity, e.g. certain value of PV cited but no reference to the correct tag number.	Little or no citing of suitable data to support claim made, or wrong data used, or no data cited whatsoever.

Figure 6. Sample Rubric for ATU Exercise

Week 2 is devoted to familiarizing students with the ATU, followed by self-paced simulation exercises that culminate in a mock assignment. To convey our expectations of what constitute a good report by students, we provided them with the marking rubric (see Figure 6). Practice marking using the rubric was carried out in class, and the students are also informed that the same rubric will be used for a graded assignment later. In Week 3, students are required to do a peer marking exercise using the rubric.

All the learning tasks for engaging students in the classroom are decided by what strategy and method combination is most likely to work best, and applied thoughtfully in terms of core principles of learning (Sale, 2015). Key strategies used include activation of prior knowledge, proving advance organizers, direct instruction, peer tutoring, and two-way feedback. In Week 3, students build on their knowledge of ATU and also learn new concepts of LOPA, namely basic process control system (BPCS) and SIS. BPCS is a topic that students had learnt before in Year 2, so we provide a brief recap so as to introduce the topic on SIS. Besides Bhopal, we also require students to re-visit the distillation pilot plant (DPP) which they had studied and operated on in an earlier module in Year 2, but now from the perspective of LOPA. Students are then taught how to apply LOPA to an equipment in ATU, namely the HP Absorber. Another activity is created whereby students can self-assess how well they apply LOPA to another equipment, this time the LP Absorber. Similarly, we continue to build-up students' knowledge and application in Week 4 (covering PRS – pressure relief system) using this approach.

As conceptual understanding is particularly important for long-term retention and transfer, we consistently revisit earlier concepts in subsequent lessons. Concept checkpoints are built into the lessons, where we pause the activity at suitable points to assess students' understanding. A checklist of learning outcomes that they need to master is shown at suitable interval during class. This checklist, together with the ongoing feedback, enables students to keep track of their own progress and take necessary corrective actions, such as completing more self-paced exercises. In this context, the use of dynamic simulation software such as EnVision has proved valuable in offering many scenarios where students can try out at a pace comfortable to each individual. A notable example was in Week 5, during which the topic of HAZOP is introduced, again using Bhopal as example, supported by other cases (such as Piper Alpha and DPP). Students are also encouraged to try out, at their own time, various ATU malfunction exercises (up to 40 available!) designed to familiarize them with potential problems in the plant, which is a key tenet of HAZOP. Sample entries are provided in Google Doc so that students are aware of the desired way to report their findings. To further strengthen their competency in carrying out a HAZOP process, a mock test is administered in Week 5, followed by peer marking of HAZOP with rubrics in Week 6. To add realism, a scoresheet (Figure 7) was also created so that students can 'officially' convey the result of the marking to the peers.

Evaluation of Student Learning Experience

Evidence-Based Reflective Practice (Sale, 2015), as the term implies, involves more than personal reflections in isolation, but a structured thinking process (e.g. analysis and evaluation) using EBT principles in relation to all valid evidence sources (e.g. students,

peers, peer observers). As a holistic process it enable a better understanding of the *reality* of classroom learning (e.g. what is happening, and how this is affecting the learning process). From this base, we can then creatively design and facilitate instructional strategies that have high predictive capability for enhancing the learning experience and attainment levels.

experiences of our student co-participants (Lincoln 1990), who have been an essential part of the on-going evaluation process. They provide a more ethnographic understanding of how students are actually experiencing what we are teaching and their perception of its usefulness from their perspective.

To date, they have provided a wide range of data on different aspects of the flipped classroom experience, but only those of most significance to this context are presented here. Overall, the students found the use of advance organizers (e.g. Figure 1) useful, although some found it difficult to understand at first. Students generally cite its usefulness in helping them to keep track of their learning progress and how the various topics are connected to form the big picture.

Students agreed that the use of self-evaluation exercises after every topic (multiple choice and/or true/false questions in Socratic) are useful. However, some students did not use these exercises the way intended – they attempted the questions after the day’s lessons instead of doing it before coming to class! As for Google Doc, students reported that classroom discussion is very useful in helping them to learn, especially from each other. This also applied to the case studies where different questions were posed to different groups, so that each group must work on one aspect of the issues presented and jointly the contribute to the solution of the whole problem. Here is a typical comment from one of the co-participants:

“Yes, the collaborative approach with regards to group discussion is indeed a much more interesting and engaging learning experience. This allows sharing of opinions and ideas, and allows each student to justify their way of thinking. With this, I was able to actively listen to others, and with their responses, make appropriate modifications to my answer in order to achieve a thorough learning ...I am able to identify faults in my arguments and answers, thereby promoting a self-marking and self-accessing approach in my own learning.”

The “chunking” of information into smaller bits, especially for the ATU, certainly helped students in understanding the ‘operation’ of the plant. Coupled with the use of rubrics for peer marking in a mock tests, this enabled students to do the necessary thinking to developing understanding of the requirements of the module. The following examples, illustrate this:

“Peer Marking with Rubrics helped me gain a better understanding of this topic area as it guided me on how to assess my peer’s answer and hence, give her feedbacks on ways of improvement. In addition, I know what is the lecturer expecting when marking for our test papers too.”

“...teammates would be able to constantly provide feedback on the answering style of different individual, hence suggesting improvements for students to improve.”

Another method that facilitated student learning was the use of DPP that activated their prior knowledge. They reported that working on the problems based on

Report received from: Class: DCHE/SA/0 ___ Group: ___	Sour gas feed from Battery Limit to LP Absorber and treated gas to Refinery Fuel Gas System		Lean DEA from Lean Amine Cooler to LP Absorber and Rich DEA to Rich Amine Flash Drum	
	Score Given	Comments to Support Score	Score Given	Comments to Support Score
Explanation on cause(s) of deviation				
Use of Evidence				
Explanation of Possible Consequences				
Use of Evidence				
Explanation of Existing Safeguard(s) Available				
Use of Evidence				
Explanation of Additional Safeguard(s) Recommended				
Use of Evidence				

Figure 7. Scoresheet for HAZOP Peer Marking

Specifically, in evaluating the learning experience we are looking for the presence or otherwise of the following:

- Appropriate method use to maximize learning opportunities in this Situated Context (e.g. learning outcomes, learner profile, learning space and resource access)?
- Clear presentation of learning goal, purpose and expectations to these learners?
- Activation of prior knowledge and subsequent connection to new knowledge presented?
- Emphasis on the key concepts and principles underpinning understand of the topic area?
- Activities (e.g. questions) that facilitated the types of thinking necessary for building understanding?
- Variation in the modes and methods of information presentation and interaction?
- Application of practices consistent with human memory processes (e.g. chunking, linkages, rehearsal and review)?
- Use of Deliberate Practice (where relevant)?
- Use of formative assessment activities to provide quality two-way feedback?
- Rapport building Interactions that promoted a climate conducive to success and some fun in the learning process?
- An aspect(s) of creativity (e.g., story, humour, activity, presentation style, example) that enhanced Intrinsic Motivation?

The evaluation of the flipped classroom is on-going and is using a range of evaluation methods to ascertain both the student learning experience and attainment. At present the data collected is from the learning

the DPP served to reinforce their learning of the safety topics in the module. The response below captures this:

“It allows us to visualise first hand, how the LOPA concepts can be applied in the DPP plant. Furthermore, it allows us to make hypothetical improvements to the DPP plant so that it encompass the LOPA concepts. This enhanced learning, as the team could discuss about the technicalities behind the DPP plant, and move on to applying LOPA.”

These in-class activities provide the lecturer with the opportunity to walk around and listen to the students' group discussions, which makes their thinking visible. In this way misconceptions can be quickly identified and dealt with and necessary checks in understanding performed. That lack of such affordance is made painfully clear in Week 3, which is a SP designated “Home-based Learning” week, where students do not come to campus for lessons but work fully online. Due to the lack of face-to-face classroom interaction, it is not possible to usefully ascertain students' ability to sketch the proper engineering diagrams depicting how SIS can be implemented. On hindsight, it would have been more effective to ask students to submit their sketches for marking. This issue was only noticed in a later week when the lecturer introduced another class activity that required students to build on this knowledge in a different application.

On the other hand, the use of checklist drew mixed responses from students. The checklist was shown in class after approximately 1 hour of lesson as mid-point summary and again as end-of-class summary. One student's response was particularly interesting:

“No, the checklist (mid-point or end of lessons) has not helped myself as individual to keep track of my learning based on the lesson objectives ...Even though, the use of a checklist does push me to think about the learning outcomes, it does not actually prove that I am indeed competent in these aspects.”

As things turned out, the lecturer often did not have sufficient time to go through the checklist in details with the class. On reflection, the checklist could have been better included in the workbook instead, for students to monitor their own learning after they had completed all the activities of a given topic.

Lastly, an important insight gained from this experience is that students tend to ‘optimize’ their time devoted to studying this module by balancing the activities designed for this module with the demand of other modules, especially those with examinations. There was one occasion where the students did not complete some simulation exercises for classroom discussion, and when inquired, they were quite frank in revealing this reason for non-submission. Also, at this time of writing, we are not able to evaluate students performance from various summative assessments.

Conclusion

The feedback from student co-participants had shown that many of the strategies employed in the teaching of *Plant Safety and Loss Prevention* via a

flipped classroom approach are positively impactful in supporting their learning, particularly the advanced organizer, use of Socratic for self-evaluation, and Google Doc for classroom group discussion.

While some (e.g. use of checklist) have not been as effective, this does not necessarily mean the method choice was inappropriate. As teaching is a highly complex and situated activity, it is always going to be heuristic, never algorithmic. However, the use of an EB approach provides our best basis for useful heuristics as it is grounded in validated knowledge relating to how humans learn and an extensive research base on method effectiveness.

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